

New Directions in Pesticide Research, Development, Management, and Policy

1993

**New Directions in Pesticide Research,
Development, Management, and Policy**

November 1-3, 1993

Program and Presenters' Abstracts

**Virginia Water Resources
Research Center**

Virginia
 Tech
VIRGINIA POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE
AND STATE UNIVERSITY

**A publication of the Virginia Water Resources Research Center,
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Diana L. Weigmann, Interim Director**

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Special recognition goes to Judy Poff for word processing, designing, and editing the abstract publication and program; S. I. Parsons for editing the abstracts; and G. W. Wills for the cover design.

COLLECTED ABSTRACTS
of the
FOURTH NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PESTICIDES

**NEW DIRECTIONS IN PESTICIDE RESEARCH,
DEVELOPMENT, MANAGEMENT, AND POLICY**

November 1-3, 1993

**Hyatt Richmond
Richmond, Virginia**

Sponsored by

**Virginia Water Resources Research Center
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University**

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AND
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- 9:00-9:45 am** **Opening — Ballroom A**
Victor Kimm, Acting Assistant Administrator, Office of Prevention, Pesticides, and Toxic Substances, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
- 9:45-10:00 am** **ADJOURN for Session Meetings**

Session Meetings

November 1, 1993

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Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

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Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

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Richmond, VA

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Well Vulnerability and Nitrate Contamination: Assessments from a Voluntary Well Testing Program

D. B. Baker¹ and R. P. Richards¹

The Heidelberg College Cooperative Private Well Testing Program is one of the largest voluntary monitoring programs of its type in the United States. It is designed to address water-quality issues in private rural wells. Through local organizations in 335 counties and 14 states, 37,000 individuals have submitted water samples to be tested as part of the program. The average nitrate-nitrogen concentration in these wells is 1.62 ppm, and 3.9 percent of the wells exceeded the drinking water standard. A concentration of 1 ppm was exceeded in about 30 percent of the wells.

The data set provides useful information regarding those factors of well vulnerability that correlate with high and low nitrate concentrations. An information sheet, completed by well owners and submitted along with their water samples, provides data on factors such as well depth, well age, well type, soil type, and proximity to cropland, feedlots, or chemical mixing sites. The data indicate that nitrate concentrations are higher in shallower wells, in older wells, in dug or driven wells, in wells located close to cropland (within 20 feet), in wells located in sandy soils, and in wells close to either feedlots or chemical mixing sites. Where wells combine the most vulnerable alternative for two or three factors, the probability of contamination by nitrate increases dramatically. For example, 27 percent of the shallow wells located in sandy soils near crops contained nitrate in excess of the drinking water standard of 10 ppm. In contrast, for deep wells in clay soils, away from cropland, nitrate-nitrogen concentrations exceeded 10 ppm in only 0.8 percent of the samples.

A mapping component of the well testing program frequently reveals spatial patterns of nitrate contamination that reflect geological factors. River valley aquifers, sandy soils with high water tables, karst areas, and reef structures with surficial expressions are all reflected in county maps that are developed as part of the program.

While voluntary programs do not necessarily provide a random sample of wells, they nevertheless provide much useful data to support local groundwater protection and education programs. In the Heidelberg program, the investments individuals make to have their own well water tested and the voluntary efforts of local agencies to facilitate the testing program are linked to the development of detailed local databases. Even though individual results remain confidential, the mapping component is adequate to support targeting groundwater protection programs.

¹Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, 310 E. Market St., Tiffin, OH 44883